

COMPOSITES AND ROADSIDE SAFETY

Development of a composite lighting column and guardrail system

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ABSTRACT

As the number of road users is increasing rapidly, a lot of research is nowadays performed on the improvement of their safety. Most research is concentrating on the vehicles, by developing new bumper systems and other safety devices like airbags. However, improvement of the passive safety of roadside structures like road signs, guardrails and lighting columns can also significantly decrease the number of road-accident casualties as errant vehicles often crash into these structures. The increasing numbers of international standards that give requirements for these structures, accelerate the need for innovations. An international consortium – including the Centre of Lightweight Structures TUD-TNO (CLS) – has developed new lighting column and guardrail systems, using composite materials to improve safety and durability and reduce maintenance costs.

The lighting column is a 10-meter high, tapered lighting column made of fiberglass/polyester. A design tool was developed that enables a swift analysis of the influence of material properties and column dimensions (e.g. wall-thickness, length, and taper) on the static behavior. A number of prototype columns were manufactured by vacuum infusion and statically tested to validate the design tool. The passive safety behavior was established by performing a 100-km/h frontal impact test by a 900-kg car. The results are twofold: the decelerations on the car were very low, which is very important for occupant safety. However, the secondary impact of the top of the column on the roof of the car caused a lot of damage. More research has to be performed to prevent this secondary impact.

Current guardrail systems that are installed along the roads can generally be divided into steel systems and concrete barriers. Steel systems can be relatively safe for passenger cars. However, most of these systems are not capable of containing heavier lorries. The concrete barriers, capable of containing the heavier vehicles are less safe for smaller vehicles resulting in higher numbers of injury accidents.

The composite guardrail system consists of several glassfiber/polyester components: a pultruded longitudinal beam, SMC posts and pultruded spacers that connect the beams with the posts. The system is designed to absorb energy in two steps. In the first step, the spacers are pushed through the posts, while material is scraped off the edges of the spacers. They therefore act as energy absorbers and can contain a 100-km/h 20° angle impact of a 900-kg car, while keeping the decelerations on the car (and the occupants) low. For heavier impacts (e.g. trucks or buses) a second step is activated. The posts rotate backward and a cone (integrated on the back part of each post) is crushed, absorbing energy at a much higher load level. Full-scale crash tests were performed on the safety fence, demonstrating that there is room for improvement for heavy impact, but giving very good results for the car impact.

KEYWORDS: Passive safety, roadside safety, crash, impact

1 INTRODUCTION

Safety in road transport has been an important issue for a long time. Much research has been performed on the improvement of safety devices of vehicles (bumper systems, airbags, etc.), while less attention has been paid to new developments in roadside safety systems. Existing roadside safety systems such as fencing, lighting columns, signs, guide rails, etc. are designed to maximize performance and minimize cost. However, there are still many deaths and serious injuries on the road

networks which indicate room for further safety advances. Accidents with lighting columns and signs can cause serious injuries to both occupants of the colliding vehicle as well as other road users. Guide rails that are currently installed can be divided into steel, flexible, systems and concrete barriers. Steel systems can be relative safe for passenger cars. However, most of these systems are not capable of containing heavier lorries causing serious danger to other traffic. The concrete barriers, capable of containing the heavier vehicles are less safe for smaller cars resulting in higher numbers of injury accidents. In general, roadside safety systems need to be further improved to increase the safety in terms of vehicle occupant survivability and reducing injury levels. The leaching of zinc from steel guide rails is a source of heavy metal pollution.

A number of companies and institutes joint forces in Ecosafe, a European research project funded under the Brite Euram framework. The overall objective of Ecosafe is to improve roadside safety systems by the versatile use of fiber reinforced polymer composite materials in these systems. More specifically Ecosafe should lead to the development of roadside safety systems that have the following benefits:

- Improved safety for all road users.
- Improved reliability, durability, maintenance and cost-effectiveness based on a through life analysis.
- Improved safety and working conditions for road maintenance personnel.
- Lower impact on the environment during its life cycle than current steel systems.

2 LIGHTING COLUMN

Introducing passive safety in lighting columns is only useful, if the column also complies with all other requirements imposed by the local governments. The objective of the Ecosafe lighting column project was to develop a column that complies with static requirements of the European standards and has an improved passive safety performance by tuning the composite material. Research focused on the column itself; development of a composite bracket arm was beyond the scope, as this part has little influence on the crash behavior. For the design calculations, a bracket had to be included and it was decided to calculate with a ‘virtual’ aluminum bracket arm.

2.1 PASSIVE SAFETY

The passive safety behavior of lighting columns is described in the European standard EN12767 ‘Passive safety of support structures for road equipment – Requirements and test methods’ (ref [10]). This standard is not a product standard, but a voluntary additional standard that gives a method to assess and specify the performance of road equipment in passive safety terms.

This standard enables a road authority, or indeed a road structure supplier, to determine the level of

Energy absorption level	Occupant safety level	Speeds			
		Mandatory low speed impact test		Speed class impact tests	
		Maximum values		Maximum values	
		ASI	THIV [kph]	ASI	THIV
HE	1	1.0	27	1.4	44
HE	2	1.0	27	1.2	33
HE	3	1.0	27	1.0	27
LE	1	1.0	27	1.4	44
LE	2	1.0	27	1.2	33
LE	3	1.0	27	1.0	27
NE	1	1.0	27	1.2	33
NE	2	1.0	27	1.0	27
NE	3	0.6	11	0.6	11
NE	4	No req.	No req.	No req.	3

Table 1: European standard EN12767 occupant safety performance classes

Column	
Height (L1)	10 m
Length below ground level (L2)	1.5 m
Diameter at ground level	250 mm
Diameter at top	76 mm
Bracket arm (if present)	
Length (L3)	1.5 m
Diameter	60 mm
Electricity system access door	
Size (height x width)	500 x 100 mm
Height above ground (lower edge)	0.5 m
Cable entry slot	
Size (height x width)	100 x 75 mm
Location below ground (center)	0.5 m
Sign	
Area	0.3 m ²
Eccentricity (from column centerline)	0.3 m

Figure 1: Lighting column dimensions

energy absorption of the road structure and the passive safety described by the Accident Severity Index (ASI) and Theoretical Head Impact Velocity (THIV). The ASI gives an indication of the accelerations that are acting on the vehicle occupants during the crash, while the THIV is the theoretical velocity at which the head of the driver hits an interior part, e.g. the steering wheel or the dashboard. The lower the values for both indicators, the safer the structure (see also table 1). Both values are calculated from the acceleration-time curves measured during the crash test. More background information on the standard is published by Simpson (ref. [2]).

2.2 DESIGN

Passively safe lighting columns are especially useful in rural areas, where average driving speeds are within the range of 80-100 km/h and columns are not protected by guard rail systems. The dimensions (diameter, height, location of electricity system access door, etc.) of columns that are installed in these areas are also applied on the Ecosafe lighting column. The selected column dimensions are listed in figure 1.

Stiffness requirements	
Max. vertical lantern displacement	$0.025 * L3$
Max. horizontal lantern displacement	$0.06 * (L1 + L3)$
Safety factors for strength calculations	
Dead loads	1.2
Wind loads	1.4
Material factor	1.5

Figure 2: Lighting column static loads and requirements

The column is designed to comply with the European Standards on static stiffness and strength (EN40-3 and EN40-7, ref. [4],[5],[6] and [7]). These standards give maximum allowable horizontal and vertical displacements of the lantern under the given loads. Relevant loads acting on the column can be divided in dead loads and wind loads. Both loads and requirements are summarized in figure 2. Calculation of the dead loads is very straightforward, but the acting wind loads (in terms of wind velocities) depend on the geographical location of the lighting column as well as the direct environment (open farmland, seashore, city, etc.). The Ecosafe lighting column is designed for locations with reference wind velocities of 28 m/s. The reference wind velocity is the 10 minutes mean wind velocity at 10 meters above ground level with an annual probability of 0.02 (i.e. having a mean return period of 50 years).

A design code was written in Mathcad to analyze the static behavior of different lighting column configurations and composite laminates under the given loads. An additional feature of this design code is the ‘translation’ of the distributed wind load on the column into discrete loads that can be applied on the column during static tests, see also section 2.3.1.

Most important aspect of the design of the column is the selection of materials and laminate. Based on cost and performance arguments, glassfibers and polyester resin were selected as the components of the composite material. Several laminates were evaluated using the design code. The selected polyester resin is the pigmented Scott Bader Crystic 701PA with UV-protector, while the reinforcement is a stitched fabric from Cotech, with mainly fibers in longitudinal direction.

2.3 PROTOTYPE TESTING

Prototypes of the column were manufactured at Swedamast, Leeuwarden (Netherlands). The applied processing technology is vacuum infusion: a low-cost closed mould composite manufacture process (ref. [1]). The prototypes were used for both static and crash testing.

2.3.1 STATIC TESTING

The post-top lighting column underwent static tests to validate the design calculations (and the software code). Buckets of sand were applied on the horizontally positioned column at intervals of 1 meter, while the column root was clamped in a block of concrete, see figure 3. The mass of the sand for each bucket was calculated from the distributed wind load. The column was loaded until cracking could be heard and local buckling at the electricity system door cutout could be seen.

The measured deflections stayed within 5% margin of the calculated deflections and the column stayed (well) within the deflection limits for a reference wind speed of 30 m/s. The column also passed the strength requirements, as failure (local buckling) did not happen until the load was increased with 9% with respect to the required load for strength.

Figure 3: Static test

2.3.2 FULL-SCALE CRASH TESTING

A 100-km/h frontal full-scale crash test was performed according to the European standard EN12767 at the crash laboratory of TNO Automotive in Delft, the Netherlands. The test vehicle was a 918 kg Renault Clio 1.2L (1992). Pictures of the crash test are shown in figure 4. Results of the test are given in table 2. From the results can be concluded that the ASI and THIV are very low, which indicates that the column has a very good passive safety performance. The measured ASI, THIV and energy absorption categorize this column according to EN12767 as being “100, LE, 3” (100-km/h speed class, Low Energy absorbing, safety level 3), assuming that the mandatory low speed impact test (table 1)

Figure 4: Video stills of full-scale 100-km/h frontal crash test

FRONTAL CRASH TEST	
Vehicle mass (Renault Clio 1.2L 1992)	918 kg
Measured impact speed	100 km/h
Measured exit speed (10 m behind point of impact)	57 km/h
Energy absorption category	Low Energy (LE)
Acceleration Severity Index (ASI)	0.59
ASI determined at averaging time window	9.8 – 59.7 msec
Theoretical Head Impact Velocity (THIV)	3.6 km/h
THIV time of flight	21.6 msec

Table 2: Summary frontal crash test

will also give good results. Safety level 3 is the highest level of safety obtainable in this particular speed and energy absorbing class.

The ASI and THIV values give information on the primary impact, where splitting of the composite enabled the column to absorb impact energy at reduced decelerations. However, the secondary impact proved to be critical during this crash test. The column folded and rotated around the front of the car, causing the upper part of the column to hit the roof of the car at a high downward velocity. This caused substantial damage to the car as visible in figure 5.

Figure 5:
Lighting column and impact vehicle after crash test

3 SAFETY FENCE

Current guardrail systems that are installed along the roads can generally be divided into steel systems and concrete barriers. Steel systems can be relatively safe for passenger cars. However, most of these systems are not capable of containing heavier lorries. The concrete barriers, capable of containing the heavier vehicles are less safe for smaller vehicles resulting in higher numbers of injury accidents. The objective of the Ecosafe safety fence project was to develop a system (of composite materials) that is gentle for occupants of impacting cars, but is also able to contain heavy impacts.

3.1 DESIGN

Requirements for a safety fence system are extensive, with restrictions on maintenance, installation and production costs, dimensions and requirements on aesthetics, durability and impact properties. For the purpose of generating design concepts and design parameters, the primary focus during the

development of the Ecosafe safety fence was the crash behavior. The fence is designed for applications at secondary roads and the European standard EN1317 (ref. [8] and [9]) prescribes two containment requirements for this road category, see table 3. Moreover, the trajectory of the vehicles after the impact must stay within the vehicle exit box as shown in figure 6.

OVERVIEW IMPACT REQUIREMENTS			
Car impact (category TB11)		Bus impact (category TB51)	
Test description	Requirements	Test description	Requirements
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vehicle mass: 900 kg Impact speed: 100 km/h Impact angle: 20° 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No breakthrough ASI < 1.4 (but preferably < 1.0) Minimized roll, yaw and pitch 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vehicle mass: 13000 kg Impact speed: 70 km/h Impact angle: 20° 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No breakthrough Deflection of the fence < 1 meter Minimized roll, yaw and pitch

Table 3: Safety fence impact requirements

Figure 6: Plan view of the impact test lay-out with vehicle exit box requirements

The most important requirement is that the vehicles must be contained and are not allowed to break through the barrier. Besides, the decelerations on the car – described by the ASI as for the lighting column test – and the deflection of the fence under a heavy vehicle are also limited. Containment of vehicles means deceleration of the vehicle until its lateral velocity (perpendicular to the direction of travel) is decreased to zero. To make this reduction of velocity possible, the safety fence has to absorb and/or dissipate the kinetic energy of the vehicle. To comply with all wishes, a two-step energy absorbing system was developed. The first step works for both the car and bus impact and absorbs energy at a relatively low force level. This ensures that the decelerations in this first stage are not too severe. This first step is sufficient to contain the car. However, this does not absorb enough energy to contain the bus. Therefore a second step is activated, where the force level increases and the absorbed energy per traveled distance as well. This two-step behavior can be translated into a force-deflection diagram as plotted in figure 7.

A number of conceptual designs were developed, all working with this two-step principle. After a trade-off between the different concepts, two designs were left. Multi-body crash simulations on these designs were performed, using two different simulation programs: MADYMO (a program developed at TNO Automotive in the Netherlands) and VEDYAC (developed at the Technical University of Milan, Italy). With these simulations, the most important components were parametrically analyzed in order to find out their behavior during TB11 and TB51 impact conditions and to be able to select the shapes and materials for the subparts of the system.

Finally, one design was selected for further development. This design uses a longitudinal beam – quite similar to the rails in most of the current steel systems – with an energy-absorbing element behind the beam: the spacer.

This spacer takes care of the first step. During activation of the second step, the post rotates (tilts) backward, thereby crushing an energy absorber that is placed at the back of the post. As the system is tilting backward, the front part with the beam increases in height, which prevents the vehicle from

Figure 7: Two-step force-deflection diagram

rolling over the safety fence system. This concept was elaborated, which resulted in the final design illustrated in figure 8. The impact behavior is shown in figure 9.

*Figure 8:
The final design of the safety fence, using
combinations of different materials and
production technologies*

The final design of the Ecosafe safety fence system consists of the following components:

Beam:

The longitudinal beam connects the posts (installed at intervals of 1 meter) with each other. The beam design is a pultruded two-cell section with flanges. The laminate consists mainly of E-glass rovings, and is completed with a small amount of continuous strand mats on the surfaces and 0/90 fabric on the front side (impact side). The applied polyester resin is Scott Bader Crystic 392.

Spacer:

The spacer keeps the beam in its place and has to absorb energy during impact in a predictable way. Energy absorption is achieved by scraping material off the edges of the spacer during the impact: the spacer is pushed by the impacting vehicle through a steel frame (which is integrated in the post) that is undersized and therefore scrapes material off the spacer. Like the beam, the spacer is also manufactured by pultrusion of glassfiber reinforced polyester (E-glass rovings and continuous strand mats) and the same resin was used: Crystic 392.

Post:

Based on mechanical properties, processability and jointing possibilities, the post was designed to consist of two identical SMC molded shells, while the energy absorbing crush cone is integrated in the post shells. The two shells are bonded to each other and are equipped with several ribs for load transfer to the crush cone. The fiber volume fraction of the SMC material used is 30%.

Ground anchor:

Based on pendulum test results on several ground anchor types placed under different angles in the soil, a design was selected. This steel anchor consists of two parts: a corrugated part below ground level and a simple beam that connects the corrugated part with the post. To ensure a predictable failure mechanism, a horizontal saw-cut was made on the front side of the upper part of the anchor just above ground level. This enables the upper part to bend backwards under heavy impacts.

Figure 9: Energy absorption of the safety fence system: in the first step (1-3) by pushing the spacer through the frame and scraping off material followed by step 2 (4-5) where the posts tilts backward, thereby crushing a cone at the back of the post.

3.2 TESTING

The energy absorbing components of the safety fence (spacer and crush cone) were tested to measure the forces and energy absorption. With the test results the dimensions were adjusted to achieve the desired properties. Pendulum tests were performed on single and double post systems to check if the total system worked in the correct sequence (spacer first, then rotation of the post and crushing of the cone). Finally, the full-scale crash tests according to European Standard EN1317 were performed by TNO Automotive at the test center of the RDW ('Rijksdienst voor het Wegverkeer') in Lelystad (Netherlands). The impacting vehicles were towed and accelerated by a truck, which released the vehicles at approximately 100 meters before the point of impact.

Figure 10: safety fence at crash site

3.2.1 BUS TEST

The safety fence failed in an early stage of the impact with the bus and the vehicle was not redirected, but continued its direction of travel, as visible in the still pictures of the digital video in figure 11. The bus was hardly decelerated by the fence. The safety fence was damaged over a length of 8 meters.

Figure 11: Impact of a 13000 kg bus, 70-km/h, measured impact angle 20°

Figure 12: Beam-beam joint

The test shows that, for this heavy vehicle, there are two major drawbacks in the design of the safety fence:

1. The beam loses its cross-sectional shape during impact thereby losing its ability to transfer loads by bending (and membrane) forces to the neighboring posts. The two flanges did not function properly, because the loading of the flanges is done by shear stresses, which are limited by the relatively low shear strength of the predominantly UD-material. Exceeding the shear strength will cause the flanges to tear loose from the other parts of the beam. Also, the compression stresses in the flanges will cause them to buckle, which limits the force they can take up.

2. The joint of the beams is insufficient. First: the steel U-connector (figure 12) only joins the rear part of the beam. The flanges are not connected, which is necessary for the main bending transfer. Secondly: the applied bolts are mainly appropriate for the transfer of shear forces. The ability of these bolts to transfer bending forces is limited: the distance between the bolts is small. To improve this joint not only the webs but also the flanges should be connected.

The resulting local failure in the beam at the place of impact and the beam-beam connection (in the test 1 meter from the place of impact) made the bus go through the safety fence and over 7 posts.

3.2.2 CAR TEST

The impact angle of the car was only 16° instead of the required 20° . This was caused by an early turn of the towing vehicle (after de-coupling the car), which then pulled the car slightly off course, resulting in a 4° deviation. Although the angle was smaller (and therefore the kinetic energy perpendicular to the safety fence as well), the results of the test are still useful, as they demonstrate that the fence behaved as expected for "low" energy impacts.

The exit angle of the car in relation to the safety fence was approximately 5° and the car remained within the limits of the vehicle exit box as mentioned in the requirements. The car activated the material scraping of about five spacers in the posts. Some of the posts and ground anchors were elastically loaded and moved somewhat in the soil on impact, to come back after the car had moved forward.

Figure 13: Impact of a 900 kg car, 100-km/h, measured impact angle 16°

Another drawback of the beam-beam connection (apart from those already mentioned in the results of the bus test) appeared in this second test. On impact the front fender of the car was compressed, but the door of the car was more resistant to this deformation. Reaching the beam-beam connection the front edge of the door acted as a slicer on the next beam section, splitting the flanges. This can be prevented when overlapping beam sections are applied, as in the steel safety fences, or by connecting also the flanges of the beam.

Overall it can be concluded that the design of the beam and the beam-beam connection must be considerably revised to withstand the higher energy impacts.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Research was performed to develop lighting columns and safety fence systems that increase roadside safety by application of composite materials. The choice for composite materials gives a durable and less polluting alternative to the common steel systems. Moreover, the composite systems are much lighter. Therefore, less installation personnel is necessary and as handling of the components is easier, installation will also be quicker and safer. The following conclusions on impact performance can be made after analysis of the full-scale crash tests on the lighting column and safety fence:

Lighting column:

The designed 10-meter lighting column complies with the EN40 requirements for both static stiffness and strength.

With respect to deceleration levels during the crash test, Low Energy level 3 passive safety performance (as described in European Standard EN12767) has been demonstrated for a 100-km/h frontal impact, which is the highest level of safety within this category.

Further development is required to avoid secondary impact and reduce the damage to the vehicle.

Safety fence:

The safety fence passed the test for a small car (although for a smaller impact angle) and the vehicle did not break through the barrier. The working principle of the spacer (scraping of the material to absorb energy) was tested and proved to be working well.

The full-scale test with the bus showed that the design of the beam (including the beam-beam joint) has to be reviewed. The actual design is not able to properly transfer the load from the vehicle to the posts.

More research needs to be conducted to determine the best option for the beam in terms of geometry (open or closed section), materials (aluminum, steel, thermoplastic or thermoset) and lay-up (UD, random, bias).

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